

SEASON-DEPENDENT RESPONSES OF FRESHWATER FISH EXPOSED TO THE ORGANOPHOSPHATE PESTICIDE CHLORPYRIFOS: A BIOCHEMICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

*The intensification of agriculture has led to the widespread use of organophosphate pesticides, chlorpyrifos being one of the most prevalent. While effective against pests, CPF runoff into freshwater ecosystems poses a significant threat to non-target organisms, particularly fish. The present study aims to evaluate the effects of sublethal exposure to chlorpyrifos on key biochemical parameters in freshwater fish, *Labeo rohita*, which serve as sensitive indicators of physiological stress and toxic impact. When compared to control groups, fish exposed to sublethal doses of chlorpyrifos for specified exposure times showed significant changes in biochemical indicators. Significant decreases in total protein levels were noted, suggesting that toxic stress impairs protein synthesis and increases proteolysis. Stress-induced hyperglycemia, which is probably caused by increased glycogenolysis in response to higher energy needs, was reflected in elevated glucose concentrations. Changes in cholesterol content indicated problems with membrane integrity and lipid metabolism. Seasonal variations were noticeable, with more significant biochemical alterations occurring during warmer months, most likely due to greater metabolic rates and pesticide absorption. These data show that chlorpyrifos causes significant metabolic stress in fish and that season influences pesticide toxicity.*

After investigation it came to light that these alterations in biochemical analysis showed variations in their parameters. This study aims to raise awareness about the perseverance mechanism of fish populations by conducting a thorough examination of these factors.

[Keywords: *pesticide, behavioral response, morphological change, biochemical parameters.*]

1. Introduction:

Fish are an important source of food of high-quality animal protein and essential nutrients for many people of India, so it is necessary to look after the health of the fish population to save the aquatic environment and biodiversity (FAO, 2020). The aquatic environment is directly responsible for better cultivation of fish farming. Since fish are frequently exposed to contaminated water and can absorb harmful compounds, these pollutants represent a major hazard to non-target aquatic animals. Pesticides are now widely used in contemporary agriculture to enhance crop output and fulfill the food demands of a fast-rising population. However, uncontrolled pesticide use has contaminated surrounding aquatic habitats via agricultural runoff, leaching, and spray drift (Aktar, Sengupta, & Chowdhury,

2009). Organophosphate pesticides are among the most widely utilized insecticides due to their efficacy against a wide range of pests. Chlorpyrifos, an often-used organophosphate insecticide, is frequently found in freshwater habitats and is known for its significant toxicity to aquatic animals even at sublethal quantities (USEPA, 2011). Fish exposed to chlorpyrifos show metabolic and morphological abnormalities, which makes them useful bioindicators for evaluating stress caused by pesticides in aquatic environments.

The physiological reactions of fish and the toxicity of pesticides are strongly influenced by seasonal change. Seasonal variations in water temperature, dissolved oxygen, and metabolic activity can affect pesticide absorption, bioavailability, and detoxifying effectiveness. While seasonal variations might influence fish's stress response, greater metabolic rates and pesticide solubility during warmer seasons may exacerbate biochemical disruptions (Singh & Sharma, 2018).

Biochemical markers such as serum protein, cholesterol, and glucose have been suggested to be sensitive indicators of metabolic and physiological changes in fish exposed to environmental pollutants. Serum protein plays an important role in development, tissue repair, and immunological function, and a decrease in protein levels is frequently related to accelerated proteolysis and reduced protein synthesis during pesticide stress (Begum, 2004). A commonly recognized stress indicator in fish, serum glucose is frequently increased after exposure to pesticides. Elevated glucose levels are a sign of stress-induced hyperglycemia brought on by increased gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis, which provide quick energy to deal with deleterious stress (Banaee, 2013). In addition to being an essential component of cell membranes, cholesterol is a precursor of steroid hormones (Das & Mukherjee, 2003).

In view of the widespread application of chlorpyrifos, the current study intends to examine the effects of sublethal chlorpyrifos exposure on specific biochemical parameters—namely, serum protein, cholesterol, and glucose—in freshwater fish, with a focus on seasonal variation, given its possible ecological risks. The results of this work will assist the use of biochemical indicators in environmental monitoring and further knowledge of pesticide-induced metabolic stress.

2. Material and Method:

Healthy and active *Labeo rohita* of mean body length 15 ± 2 cm and mean body weight 148 ± 21 gm were collected from a local pond in Patna, and the organophosphate pesticide chlorpyrifos (CPF), CPF 20% EC, was used for this experiment. Four large aquariums of size $4 \times 3 \times 3$ were taken. After the collection from the pond, live *Labeo rohita* were immediately carried in polybags containing additional dissolved oxygen to the research laboratory and transferred to the aquarium and disinfected with a 0.1% KMnO_4 solution. They were acclimatized in research laboratory conditions for 10 days. The fish were properly fed with fish food products during morning and evening hours of the day. The LC_{50} of chlorpyrifos for the *Labeo rohita* was calculated as per the standard method of APHA (2012). The sublethal concentration of chlorpyrifos was chosen during our study. For biochemical studies, such as serum protein, cholesterol content, and glucose content, were determined by spectrophotometric assays using their respective commercially available kits for different biochemical studies after separating serum by centrifugation of the blood sample. In the case of serum protein, Biuret reagent was used and calculates the protein concentration in the sample through the Biuret method. For

examination of cholesterol content in the sample, a reagent containing cholesterol oxidase was used at the wavelength 540 nm in a colorimeter, and by using the formula provided in the kit protocol, cholesterol content was determined. Glucose content was examined and calculated by the glucose enzymatic method.

3. Result:

The biochemical parameters of *Labeo rohita* exposed to a sublethal dose of chlorpyrifos during the summer season were tabulated in Table 1.

Through this study, it was found that the exposure to a sublethal dose of chlorpyrifos caused severe changes, including elevation in glucose and cholesterol concentration. While it showed a significant decrease in protein content after pesticide exposure. The level of significance statistically calculated was ($P < 0.05$) for 15 days and ($P < 0.01$) and ($P < 0.001$) for 30 days, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Biochemical parameters of *Labeo rohita* during the summer season of control and treated with chlorpyrifos for 15 and 30 days.

Parameters	Control (15d)	Treated (15d)	Control(30d)	Treated (30d)
Serum Protein (g/dl)	3.97 ± 0.17	3.46 ± 0.23*	3.92 ± 0.16	2.97 ± 0.29***
Cholesterol Content (mg/dl)	94 ± 5.83	104.8 ± 4.14**	92 ± 5.6	112.6 ± 3.97***
Glucose Content (mg/dl)	83 ± 5.7	97 ± 7.2**	81 ± 5.5	114 ± 9.62***

Each value is the mean ± S.D. of five estimations. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$

Table 2 shows the effect of chlorpyrifos on different blood parameters and their indices after 15 and 30 days of exposure during the monsoon season. The value of serum protein significantly dropped ($p < 0.05$) and ($p < 0.001$) after 15 and 30 days, whereas glucose content and cholesterol content were found to significantly increase ($p < 0.01$) and ($p < 0.001$) after 15 and 30 days.

Table 2: Biochemical parameters of *Labeo rohita* during the monsoon season of the control and treated with chlorpyrifos for 15 and 30 days.

Parameters	Control (15d)	Treated (15d)	Control(30d)	Treated (30d)
Serum Protein (g/dl)	3.64 ± 0.47	3.08 ± 0.47*	3.58 ± 0.45	2.78 ± 0.19***
Cholesterol Content (mg/dl)	101.2 ± 6.3	114.6 ± 5.72**	100.5 ± 6.1	123.4 ± 5.45**
Glucose Content (mg/dl)	70 ± 3.8	75 ± 3.8*	69 ± 3.7	90 ± 3.8***

Each value is the mean ± S.D of five estimations. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$

Table 3: Biochemical parameters of *Labeo rohita* during the winter season of the control and treated with chlorpyrifos for 15 and 30 days.

Parameters	Control (15d)	Treated (15d)	Control(30d)	Treated (30d)
Serum Protein (g/dl)	2.86 ± 0.23	2.51 ± 0.26*	2.82 ± 0.22	2.33 ± 0.23**
Cholesterol Content (mg/dl)	106.6 ± 3.78	118.20 ± 2.86**	105.8 ± 3.7	126.20 ± 2.86**
Glucose Content (mg/dl)	75 ± 4.47	94.20 ± 3.19**	74 ± 4.4	118 ± 5.01***

Each value is the mean ± S.D of five estimations * P<0.05, ** P<0.01, * P<0.001**

The changes in biochemical parameters during the monsoon season are shown in Table 3. The highest significant difference was shown in glucose content ($p < 0.01$) after 15 and ($p < 0.001$) after 30 days of exposure. The value of serum proteins significantly dropped under the stress of chlorpyrifos, whereas the cholesterol content was reported to have significantly increased in number after pesticide exposure ($p < 0.01$) and ($p < 0.001$) after 15 and 30 days.

Comparative result of biochemical parameters of three seasons:

According to a comparative investigation of biochemical markers, fish exposed to chlorpyrifos showed distinct seasonal fluctuations in blood protein, glucose, and cholesterol levels. All treatment groups' serum protein levels were trending downward throughout the course of the seasons when compared to their corresponding controls. While somewhat greater protein levels were noted during the summer season, the decrease was more noticeable during the winter and the monsoon. This decline suggests higher protein use to satisfy elevated metabolic needs under stress induced by pesticides, especially in warmer climates.

During all three seasons, fish exposed to pesticides had significantly higher serum glucose levels than controls. Summer had the greatest glucose concentration, followed by winter, while monsoon had the lowest rise. Increased glycogenolysis and gluconeogenesis to deal with toxic stress, which is exacerbated by higher temperatures, are suggested by the raised glucose levels, which represent a stress-induced hyperglycemic response.

Fish treated with chlorpyrifos had an apparent rise in cholesterol content throughout the year. The monsoon season saw the most increase in cholesterol levels, suggesting increased lipid usage and potential modification of lipid metabolism under pesticide stress. Winter had moderate changes, whilst summer saw relatively smaller changes.

4. Graphical representation of seasonal variation in Biochemical parameters of *Labeo rohita* after 30 days of exposure

Fig. 1: Seasonal variation in total Serum Protein of *Labeo rohita* after 30 days of exposure

Fig. 2: Seasonal variation in total Cholesterol content of *Labeo rohita* after 30 days of exposure

Fig. 3: Seasonal variation in total Cholesterol content of *Labeo rohita* after 30 days of exposure

5. Discussion:

Biochemical parameters are important for toxicological research and have been widely used in environmental monitoring, as they reflect early metabolic and physiological disturbances caused by toxic exposure (Banaee, 2013). In the present investigation, exposure to chlorpyrifos has been shown to significantly change fish biochemical markers, indicating physiological and metabolic stress. Chlorpyrifos at sublethal quantities interferes with the metabolism of glucose, proteins, and cholesterol, resulting in lower blood protein and cholesterol levels and higher glucose levels. While raised glucose levels reflect a stress-induced hyperglycemic response intended to fulfill increased energy needs, decreased protein levels suggest increased proteolysis and reduced protein synthesis, and alterations in cholesterol content suggest disturbances in lipid metabolism and membrane integrity. This result was supported by many studies that have demonstrated alterations in biochemical parameters in fish as a result of the presence of contaminants such as chlorpyrifos in aquatic habitats (Begum, 2004; Das & Mukherjee, 2003; Banaee, 2013; Velmurugan et al., 2009). These metabolic alterations act as early warning indicators of pesticidal stress in aquatic species and are sensitive biomarkers of chlorpyrifos-induced harm (Rao et al., 2005).

Conclusion:

The current study clearly demonstrates that fish exposed to the organophosphate insecticide chlorpyrifos have notable changes in important biochemical indicators, suggesting severe metabolic and physiological stress. Serum protein consistently decreased after sublethal exposure to chlorpyrifos, indicating increased proteolysis and compromised protein synthesis. Serum glucose levels and cholesterol levels, on the other hand, were noticeably elevated,

indicating a hyperglycemic response brought on by stress and disturbance of lipid metabolism. that aims to satisfy elevated energy needs in hazardous environments.

Overall, the results show that serum protein, glucose, and cholesterol are sensitive and accurate biochemical markers of chlorpyrifos-induced pesticidal stress in fish. The study underlines the ecological danger of chlorpyrifos contamination in freshwater ecosystems, as well as the significance of taking seasonal variation into account when assessing pesticide toxicity. To protect aquatic life and sustain ecosystem health, pesticides must be monitored continuously and used sparingly.

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